

AI-Driven Honeypot: An Innovative Approach to Adaptive Cyber Security Defence

Honeypot impulsado por IA: un enfoque innovador para la defensa adaptativa de la ciberseguridad

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Abstract— As cyber threats continue to grow in sophistication, the need for intelligent and adaptive defence mechanisms becomes increasingly more critical. This project investigates the integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) into a honeypot system to distract, mislead through deception, and engage potential cyber attackers. The primary research question to answer was: “How can AI-driven adaptive deception improve the effectiveness of honeypots in cybersecurity?”

To address this, a high-interaction honeypot was developed on a HTML website to be perceived as a reverse shell, with the implementation of OpenAI’s GPT-4o model to respond, impersonating a Linux terminal, whilst silently tracking and logging the attacker, and classifying all commands into three sub-categories – Safe, Suspicious and Malicious. The core methods included command logging, AI-driven risk classification, dynamic fake filesystem manipulation, and the escalation of behaviour based on the attacker’s actions. Attack simulations were performed by highly credible third-party cybersecurity experts to evaluate the honeypots effectiveness in engaging and tracking the attacker for as long as possible.

The findings suggest that AI integration significantly improved the realism and engagement level of the honeypot, both in terms of enhancing intelligence gathering and the improvements from traditional static honeypots. However, full automation of behavioural escalation tuning remained an area to further explore. Overall, this study demonstrates that the integration of AI within traditional honeypot strategies can significantly enhance cyber defence systems.

Keywords— honeypot, artificial intelligence, cybersecurity, adaptive deception, GPT-4o, intrusion detection

Resumen— A medida que las ciberamenazas se vuelven cada vez más sofisticadas, la necesidad de mecanismos de defensa inteligentes y adaptativos se vuelve cada vez más crítica. Este proyecto investiga la integración de la Inteligencia Artificial (IA) en un sistema honeypot para distraer, engañar y atraer a posibles ciberatacantes. La principal pregunta de investigación fue: “¿Cómo puede el engaño adaptativo basado en IA mejorar la eficacia de los honeypots en ciberseguridad?”.

Para abordar esto, se desarrolló un honeypot de alta interacción en un sitio web HTML para que se percibiera como un shell inverso. Se implementó el modelo GPT-4o de OpenAI para responder, suplantando una terminal Linux, rastreando y registrando silenciosamente al atacante y clasificando todos los comandos en tres subcategorías: seguro, sospechoso y malicioso. Los métodos principales incluyeron el registro de comandos, la clasificación de riesgos basada en IA, la manipulación dinámica de sistemas de archivos falsos y la escalada del comportamiento en función de las acciones del atacante. Expertos externos en ciberseguridad de alta credibilidad realizaron simulaciones de ataques para evaluar la eficacia de los honeypots a la hora de interactuar y rastrear al atacante durante el mayor tiempo posible.

Los resultados sugieren que la integración de la IA mejoró significativamente el realismo y el nivel de interacción del honeypot, tanto en términos de mejora de la recopilación de inteligencia como en comparación con los honeypots estáticos tradicionales. Sin embargo, la automatización completa del ajuste de la escalada del comportamiento sigue siendo un área que requiere mayor exploración. En general, este estudio demuestra que la integración de la IA en las estrategias tradicionales de honeypots puede mejorar significativamente los sistemas de ciberdefensa.

Keywords— honeypot, inteligencia artificial, ciberseguridad, engaño adaptativo, GPT-4o, detección de intrusiones

I. INTRODUCTION

The cybersecurity landscape is an ever-evolving environment, with attacks on systems rapidly becoming more sophisticated and advanced. To combat the development of malicious threats, cybersecurity is required to constantly evolve and adapt, to stay ahead of emerging risks. A successful tested example of achieving this is the honeypot concept.

Reference [1] defines a honeypot as an information system or system resource, designed to serve as being an attractive target for attacks. The purpose of a honeypot is to detect, analyse and distract cyber attackers from gaining unauthorised access to the real system (CSRC (n.d.)). This determines a

honeypot being an incredibly important resource to implement, as it can collect data to analyse attackers' tactics through their interaction with the honeypot, gaining insights into attack patterns, tools and techniques used, to help improve and develop the systems defence strategies. A honeypot will also slow down the attacker's progress through diversion and deception, wasting their time and efforts, frustrating the attacker, reducing the risk of attacks on the real infrastructure of the system.

Within cybersecurity, deception has historically been applied from the earliest honeypots, such as Fred Cohen's Deception Toolkit in 1998, which provided fake services as a decoy machine [2]. Over time, honeypots advanced to become more sophisticated, like Honeyd, which simulated networks and devices. However, in parallel, cyberattacks have become more advanced too, and a concern of uprising limitations within static honeypots have become too apparent. The introduction of machine learning and Artificial Intelligence (AI) being implemented into a honeypot is proving to be the next evolutionary movement, that can combat the complexity of new, advanced cyber threats [3].

Despite the growing application of AI in cybersecurity, combining AI with Reinforcement Learning (RL) is relatively unexplored. Research from [4] suggested RL as a machine learning paradigm which identifies the optimal policy based on an action, shown by an action (a_t) in state (s_t), leading to the optimal policy maximising the reward ($R(s_t, a_t)$). After a training process, the RL model interacts until finding the optimal policy.

Reinforcement Learning has proven to be very efficient, evidenced by a survey from [5] that compared RL algorithms, including AdaBoost. They concluded that the AdaBoost algorithm achieved a low false positive rate (between 2.7% - 3.5%) and a high detection rate (between 90% - 99.3%). Whilst AdaBoost is not used within this project, the study highlights the suitability of machine learning to detect and classify commands and attacks, which this study will explore.

Static honeypots are defined as honeypots with predefined, unadaptable behavioural responses, regardless of the attacker's interactions. According to [6], these types of honeypots being used for detection or deception, can maximise effectiveness using the Japonica framework. However, these static honeypots can be revealed easily by attackers from fingerprinting, which is the process of identifying unique characteristics of the honeypot, or probing, to expose the honeypot. In contrast, an AI-enhanced honeypot, particularly those utilising RL, which can adapt with dynamic responses from real-time analysis of an attacker's behaviour. This is a gap to explore in the development of cyber security defences to stay ahead of the adapting threats.

Honeypots can be classified into low-interaction and high-interaction systems. Low-interaction honeypots are limited to static services or responses, which are easily fingerprinted, whilst high interaction systems provide a realistic environment that allows an attacker to interact with a real operating system or an emulated one. Recent work from [7] describe high interaction honeypots as being capable of obtaining rich data, gaining insights into attacker behaviour and tactics. The evolution of honeypots is crucial to modern threat intelligence, as low-interaction honeypots are much less efficient and stealthy than adaptive, intelligent high interactive

honeypots, creating a need for enhanced honeypot systems. However, [7] also discuss the risk that high-interactive honeypots propose massive security risks to the actual network environment, for example, a real shell being exposed. To address this risk, a honeypot being deployed on port 80 to appear as a web interface provides the honeypot to contain no risk associated with Secure Socket Shell (SSH) connections, whilst still appearing as the system terminal.

This research aims to develop an AI-enhanced honeypot that detects, analyses, and adapts using a heuristic deception policy in conjunction with the AI model to become as stealthy, realistic and efficient as possible. The objectives of this honeypot include the implementation of Cowrie on Port 22 to provide another version of a honeypot to the intended main web interface honeypot, which aims to be able to use AI to respond to attackers, whilst recording, classifying, and analysing all data and adapting using deception strategies as a result. This project explores how a honeypot can escape being easily fingerprinted, through adaptation by modifying its behaviour based on an attacker interaction, making the deception more effective.

The research will be guided by four key questions that need to be addressed:

- Can the integration of Artificial Intelligence effectively deceive attackers through the ability to become adaptable and realistic?
- Can an AI-controlled honeypot collect higher quality data when compared to a static honeypot?
- Does AI-enhancement identify and classify commands effectively?
- How effective is an adaptive, heuristic-driven deception module in responding more intelligently to attacker behaviour over time, to prolong attacker engagement and improve attacker deception?

The scope of the project includes AI classification, an SSH honeypot, reverse shell simulation with AI-generated responses, and attacker logging. There are also some limitations of this project however, including that the honeypot shall be deployed on a controlled network, not in a live network, and therefore the attacks that will test it are simulated instead of a real advanced persistent threat from external sources, with the intended set-up of the network shown in Figure 1.

Fig. 1. AI-driven honeypot intended framework

This research contributes to the rapidly growing cybersecurity field in intelligence defence by demonstrating how AI can offer insights with adaption, deception, data collection and classification.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

This literature review explores how much of an impact the introduction of AI can have and how it can be integrated within cybersecurity honeypots.

The purpose of this literature review is to understand the current reliable research relating to the efficiency of AI-controlled honeypots, their comparison to traditional honeypots, as well as aiming to understand different strategies, implementation, and findings that have been concluded within AI driven honeypots. The objective of the literature review is to analyse and understand the current state of work completed within this sector, growing trends, and to discover potential gaps where this research can focus on. As the use of AI in honeypots is relatively new, the literature review will focus on recent publications, from the initial frameworks to the more recent use of adaptive intelligence and real-time response.

A. Honeypot Framework

Honeypots have accomplished the reputation of being a valuable tool to attract, deceive, and analyse attackers. However, their effectiveness is decreasing due to advancements in fingerprinting techniques, which can identify a honeypot. Reference [8] present a comprehensive study on honeypot fingerprinting in 'Gotta Catch 'em All', using a multi-stage framework. The multistage framework evaluates fingerprinting on honeypots across the network layers of the OSI model and assesses typical honeypot implementations and detects inconsistencies within protocols, network responses, and delays to reveal the honeypots as what they are. The proposed solutions to the exposed indications of honeypots like Cowrie or Dionaea, consists of Protocol Obfuscation, which is altering network responses to mimic real systems, and Behaviour Randomisation, which is introducing variability in responses, interactions and delays to attempt to mitigate fingerprinting. The research shows the importance of adaptability and realism within honeypot deployment to keep up with the evolving use of malicious techniques, however AI or adaptive deception is not incorporated in this particular research, signalling an opportunity to further explore and improve using intelligent models.

B. Use of Large Language Models (LLM) in Deception Systems

Recent work in LLMs have driven a new wave of high-interaction honeypots. Reference [9] concluded that by fine-tuning an open source LLM with data from attacker commands, a honeypot can effectively generate realistic AI responses, demonstrating the potential of LLM's to improve threat detection and analysis. Their results show promise in enhancing realism and engagement within honeypots, although the LLM may be vulnerable to fingerprinting, highlighting a potential gap for synthesis with combining [8] fingerprint evasion strategies.

Similarly, [10] investigated GPT-3.5 in an SSH-based environment. The method consisted of analysing 1,400 request-response pairs across three datasets using GPT-3.5, finding that while it maintained context within outputs, it

struggled with long-session coherence and realism. After adapting a paraphrase-mining approach, they achieved a macro F1 score of 77.85%, which is used to evaluate the performance of the model in terms of precision and recall. The higher the percentage, the more convincing LLM generated response, leaving a valuable potential gap to improve.

However, in contrast, [11] found that the implementation of LLMs is capable of more realistic interactions, by producing a LLM (LLMPot) that effectively emulates ICS protocols. ICS networks are vulnerable to cyber-attacks due to ease of connectivity, therefore the LLMPot was introduced to implement dynamic protocol emulation, in real-time. The results suggest that while LLMs were challenged by SSH environments, they were very effective for more structured, protocol-based honeypots like ICS. Unlike [9] generalised interaction model, LLMPot's interactive approach conclude that context-specific honeypots benefit from specialised models, whilst multi-vector, adaptive honeypots benefit from generalised intelligence.

In addition to this research, [12] developed 'DecoyPot', a honeypot that simulates API interactions in web environments using LLMs. The system proved to be highly engaging and therefore demonstrated potential in how generative models can be highly functional in a HTTP-based services, directly aligning with this research into creating a web-interfaced fake reverse shell, and how effective LLMs can be within highly interactive honeypots.

The literature review has shown that each approach to evaluate LLM-driven honeypots can be thought of as different frameworks in different ways. Whilst [9] and [11] both prioritise improving the realism in honeypots; however, they differ between flexibility and being domain specific. In contrast, [10] looks at establishing a standardized methodology, ensuring both scalability and replication.

C. Adaptive Intelligence and Real-Time Response

Beyond LLMs, broader AI-based honeypots have gained traction in the last year. Reference [13] found that traditional honeypots that rely on static configurations are becoming less effective against advanced and evolving cyberattacks. Their AI-driven model collected over 100 GB of data in 24 hours and maintained attacker interaction for 40% longer than static honeypots and had a 90% detection rate, compared to the 65% rate for static honeypots. These results reinforce the critical effectiveness of adaptive honeypots, from defending against a range of zero-day exploits, advanced persistent threats (APTs) and polymorphic malware. The study split the framework of the model into different layers: External attackers (This study used real cyber-attacks, however this research intends to use simulated local attacks to test it locally), Honeypot Interaction Environment (the AI makes responses based on the attack, comparable to this intended honeypot), Data Collection Layer (this layer captures network traffic, interactions and attack data, which is crucial to recording results), Security Analyst (threat intelligence gathering from data collected in the Data Collection Layer), and AI-Based Adaptation Engine (AI process data to adapt honeypot behaviour in real-time). This blueprint can be used to effectively to simulate an AI-driven adaptive honeypot that is more efficient than a static honeypot.

Supportive of [13] research from [14] assessed using AI-enhanced honeypots to address zero-day exploits. Traditional honeypots are often not dynamic enough to challenge these types of exploits; however, the AI-controlled honeypot was

successful in predicting exploit attempts in real-time. The AI-enhanced honeypot achieved a 92% detection rate for zero-day exploits, whilst traditional honeypots got 75%, highlighting the significant improvement these types of honeypots can achieve. However, the AI algorithm found a high number of false negatives in the study, which negatively impacts the integrity and reliability of the AI. This study outlines the clear difference between the two honeypots and highlights the importance of honeypots being adaptable using AI. It provides valuable insights from which any future research can be built on, especially the importance of recognising how false negatives could become a problem.

In addition to external threats, internal threats also require real-time cybersecurity precautions. Reference [15] address how sophisticated internal threats need real-time, efficient cyber security measures in place. The study uses real SSH honeypot logs mapped to the MITRE ATT&CK framework, leveraging Retrieval-Augmented Generation (RAG) and K-Means clustering to classify attacker behaviour. The advantage of this research is how the use of high-interaction honeypots that use an AI-driven approach to automate data analysis, can lead to detecting threats as quickly as possible, leading to quicker incident responses to mitigate the threats, to enhance anonymity detection. However, the disadvantage of this paper is that it only detects a specific type of attack, for instance, not recognising DoS attacks.

D. Implementation of ChatGPT within honeypots

Other studies have explored the use of generative AI, such as ChatGPT (model GPT-3.5) within honeypots. In an educational seminar from [16] they demonstrate how an AI controlled honeypot can mimic a Linux server. The seminar demonstrates how, after a potential attacker puts a malicious script in the HTTP server to create a reverse shell, the attacker begins unknowingly, to interact with ChatGPT, distracting and misleading them. However, their system could be easily broken using prompt injection, and could not handle file uploads or network requests, highlighting a potential gap to explore and solve.

Further evaluation of ChatGPT's potential in honeypots was conducted by [17] who mapped Elasticsearch and SSH honeypot logs to the MITRE ATT&CK framework. In two weeks, 627 Elasticsearch requests and 73 SSH attack sequences were examined, finding that whilst the MITRE ATT&CK Mapping accuracy was 72.46% for Elasticsearch and 98.84% SSH accuracy, ChatGPT achieved 96.65% Elasticsearch and 97.26% SSH accuracy, proving to be crucially important in Elasticsearch logging, with little difference in SSH logging. In terms of obfuscation detection, ChatGPT did identify the obfuscation well, however also recorded a high number of false positives (30.46% of request bodies and 7.5% of targeted URIs falsely recorded), which aligns with findings from [14], supporting the issue around AI-driven honeypots recording false negatives. To conclude, ChatGPT was effective for automated honeypot analysis, but had a big setback with the high false positive rate, allowing for future work to investigate their role in incident response. The false positive setback proves to be a big weakness in AI-driven honeypots across multiple studies and is something to consider for this dissertation.

E. Synthesis of Findings and Research Gaps

This literature review highlights different findings and problems that can be later explored in the methodology. This dissertation aims to use this research and design in a similar way and to help mitigate against being so vulnerable to prompt injection and enhance the other weaknesses. These findings and issues consist of the following:

- The use of AI recording a high number of false positives.
- How prompt injection can easily detect the use of AI instead of a real system.
- How a high-interaction honeypot can keep attackers engaged.
- How AI can detect threats to log and report, in a rapid, efficient way.
- The most efficient framework for a high-interaction honeypot to be as realistic as possible.

Lastly, the literature review identified what makes an effective AI-driven honeypot and it is critical these learnings are considered at the design phase.

- Adaptability: [13] and [14] presented using adaptive and AI models that adaptability significantly improves performance metrics.
- Balancing realism and security: [9] created a high-interactive, realistic honeypots, but this came with the flaw of being vulnerable to prompt injection and fingerprinting, which [8] explored but concluded fingerprinting cannot be completely mitigated against.
- AI in Detection and Analysis: Research showed through RAG and K-Means clustering [15] and ChatGPT classification [17] that AI can effectively identify, classify and report attacks, however, did suffer from accuracy.

III. METHODOLOGY

A. Introduction

This section will cover the methodology of the project, outlining the tools and techniques used to create the project, and the data it produced. The project aims to fulfil the gaps highlighted in the literature review, creating an AI-controlled honeypot that responds to attackers in the most realistic method as possible, without being broken by prompt injection, as well as recording the data as efficiently as possible, without frequent false positives. This methodology was also guided by the four key questions that needed to be addressed, highlighted in the introduction.

B. Research Design and Approach

1) Honeypot Design

An experimental design was adapted to implement AI and enhance the honeypot system. This approach consisted of:

- Setting up an Ubuntu Linux Server and an Ubuntu Linux Desktop on the same network.
- The creation of a HTTP web page
- The implementation of Cowrie on Port 22
- Developing a web-based fake reverse shell to capture attackers

- Implementation of GPT-4o to setup to act like a Linux server and adapt to the threats. The GPT-4o model was chosen as in the literature review, because the GPT models from the literature review used model GPT-3.5, which worked, however found prompt injection to be a critical limitation, as well as recording high false positives [14], [16]. The GPT-4o model is also more intelligent within its responses.
- The GPT-4o model was implemented in three separate sections to provide three different functions: To respond to commands, to classify commands, and to generate fake files. Each model would require unique training to its unique task.
- The collection of the data that the honeypot collected that can be monitored and analysed in real-time, including the GPT-4o model which would identify risk level of commands entered to the categories: Safe, Suspicious or Malicious.
- Allowing the attacker some privileges, such as the creation and deletion of both directories and files, to keep the attacker engaged.
- Development of the honeypot to adapt, based on interactions with it.

Figure 2 illustrates the structured design of the honeypot for the two use cases of how an attacker would interact with the honeypot.

Fig. 2. Framework of Methodology

Fig. 3. AI-Driven Honeypot Flowchart

Figure 3 displays the framework of how the honeypot functions, deployed on Port 80, from when a command is entered to the output it responds with.

The most crucial and key issue that was identified from the literature review for this project to function efficiently was making sure the prompt injection could not be broken. Whilst researched studies used GPT-3.5, this project implemented GPT-4o to mitigate against prompt injection that causes the AI to break character. Reference [17] conducted an exam, testing different models' abilities to understand and generate language, particularly in complex scenarios. Whilst GPT-3.5 scored in the bottom 10%, GPT-4o scored in the top 10%,

highlighting the difference and need for a smarter model to be implemented. As such, GPT-4.0 has been used in the design.

C. Tools and Techniques

1) Network Configuration

In a controlled environment that was created for this project, a Linux Ubuntu Server and a Linux Ubuntu Desktop were created on the same internal network, using Oracle VirtualBox. The honeypot was deployed onto the server and configured such that, after an Nmap scan, it displays ports 22 and 80 as open, so that an attacker believes they have a couple of entry points to the server.

2) SSH Honeypot Deployment

On Port 22, Cowrie was downloaded, which (GitHub - Cowrie/Cowrie: Cowrie SSH/Telnet Honeypot <https://docs.cowrie.org/>, n.d.) is a virtual SSH-based honeypot, designed to log brute force attacks. Cowrie was integrated as it simulates a SSH login system, emulating a session, however, will never grant SSH access, but instead observes the attacker by logging behaviour and passwords inputted on a simulated UNIX system, [19]. Another advantage of Cowrie is that it can generate structured, detailed logs to gain meaningful insight into attacker behaviour and tactics and achieved an f1-score of 89.8% as found from a study from [20], proving Cowrie’s effectiveness in collecting highly reliable data. Reference [19] further supports the effectiveness of Cowrie, concluding that their Support Vector Machine achieved a classification accuracy of 97.39%, highlighting Cowrie’s role in AI-enhanced intrusion detection.

3) Web-Based Reverse Shell on Port 80

In addition, on Port 80, a Flask-Based Web Server was set up using Python, for the web-based fake reverse shell to be established there. This Fake Reverse Shell was the main component of this dissertation, where an attacker is tricked into interacting with the AI-controlled honeypot, which uses GPT-4.0 to simulate exactly what a real Linux server would look and respond like and adapt to the attackers’ movements. All commands and AI-generated responses are logged and analysed by an AI model.

The code was completed primarily using Python, due to:

- Extensive Libraries Supported, including web development frameworks like Flask, which was used because of its ease to deploy and integrate both the web-based interface and adaptive AI [21], as well as mimicking real world web exploits.
- Ease of applying AI and machine learning integration.
- Prototyping – ease of debugging, [22].

The code consists of the creation of a HTML website to appear as a reverse shell on the servers IP address, with AI implemented to respond to all commands inputted into it to simulate the real server, as well as AI to log and determine risk level of each command.

The code also allowed for certain escalated privileges, such as creating and deleting both files and directories, in order to keep the attacker engaged by misleading them into thinking they have some privileges and therefore deceive them into thinking privilege escalation on the server may be

possible. The code also enabled the AI to generate fake files based off the filename.

The honeypot is displayed as shown in Figure 4 – The terminal HTML appears as a reverse shell as the user ‘Dave’ to manipulate attackers.

Fig. 4. The AI-controlled Web-based reverse shell

4) AI-driven Adaptive Deception

Initially, a static honeypot was deployed with predefined responses to test connections, whilst a basic keyword-matching method and a ‘suspicious threshold’, which would implement after the quantity of commands increased, was used to detect suspicious command patterns. Once this was working correctly, a rule-based adaptive policy, driven by command-classification thresholds and LLM-generated responses was developed to be able to dynamically adjust responses, based on the attacker’s interaction. Both suspicious and malicious command types are flagged and categorised by the GPT-4o AI model. To assess the effectiveness of the adaptive deception model, it was tested in comparison to the original static honeypot. The metrics included the quantity of suspicious and safe commands, risk level success rate, and attacker session duration. This test concluded that the AI’s decision making was much more advanced and reliable, increasing the validity and therefore the performance of the honeypot. The suspicious threshold was maintained, as it tracks the user via the client IP count and flags them once they exceed the threshold, alerting the IP address as a likely attacker.

The adaptive module’s main focus, however, was to generate responses that the honeypot would output, instead of using Flask’s application that used static, rule-based, predefined responses. The adaptive model was built to learn from attacker behaviour in real time so it can adapt and dynamically generate outputs based on attacker behaviour. This can then keep the attacker engaged for the maximum time as well as track the attackers’ steps and behaviour, proving to be much more efficient. The adaptability of the honeypot was implemented through tracking the attacker’s state, such as the IP addresses deception level, suspicious threshold, and session, and changing over these variables.

An example of the AI-driven adaptive deception implemented was to monitor behaviour from a suspected IP address trying to open files, which then triggered password prompts, which in turn would further escalate the honeypot’s hints and ‘potential weaknesses’ to make the attacker believe that they are getting somewhere with the attack. The attacker would then be consistently finding what they believe to be

new information, without realising it is all generated information. This is crucial in keeping the attacker engaged in the honeypot for as long as possible.

5) *Tools and Techniques to simulate attacks on the honeypot*

- Nmap was originally used to perform reconnaissance and gather information on open ports.
- Attempts to SSH into the server or creating a reverse shell on the client machine.
- Linux commands such as ‘ls’, ‘cd’ ‘whoami’ which are considered as non-malicious, to navigate the system, and determine if the AI classifies these commands as usual behaviour.
- Malicious Linux commands such as ‘wget’, ‘reboot’, ‘rm’ to verify the honeypot is classifying the IP as an attacker, and that the honeypot adapts to the specific command, responding in a realistic manner.

D. Data Collection and Analysis

All activity and interactions were logged in real-time through Flask’s logging methods. This data can be accessed in the server but was also mapped to a comma delimited text (CSV) file.

The developed software classifies the following data elements:

Element	Example of Output
ID	1
Timestamp	2025-03-12 02:22:03
IP Address	30.30.0.1
Command	whoami
Risk Level	Suspicious
Current Directory	home
Response	Dave

TABLE I. DATA THAT THE HONEYPOT LOGS

The risk level was determined by the GPT-4o AI model, as instructed to define what level of risk each command should be classified as, between Safe, Suspicious, and Malicious.

All SSH login attempts on port 22 were logged via Cowrie logs.

E. Ethical Considerations

1) *Lab set-up*

To ensure ethical compliance, the honeypot was deployed in a controlled lab environment that was set up just for this project. This prevents the honeypot from being accessed over the internet or any University network, avoiding unethical cybersecurity practices and limiting external factors. The collection of data adhered to privacy and legal standards, without the use of personally identifiable information.

2) *AI Jailbreaking*

Reference [23] states that AI jailbreaking refers to a technique in manipulating AI models to bypass restrictions, causing the system to execute malicious instructions which may violate relative policies and produce harmful outputs. It was noted that this research could be subject to attackers manipulating the AI-controlled honeypot to leak sensitive information or creating harmful content.

However, [18] does suggest that whilst AI jailbreaks are a big problem for GPT models, they found that the model GPT-4o has a considerably lower amount of incorrect behaviour rate on disallowed or sensitive content, as illustrated in Figure 5.

Fig. 5. Rate of incorrect behaviour on sensitive and disallowed prompts. Lower values are better GPT-4 RLHF has much lower incorrect behaviour rate compared to prior models

Therefore, through using the more advanced GPT-4o model instead of the 3.5 model, as well as flagging potential attempts to manipulate the AI, can mitigate against the threat of AI jailbreaks.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Introduction

This section will present data that the honeypot produced through logs, adaption from attacker behaviour, AI decisions, and the effectiveness of the honeypot at appearing realistic and deceptive. Results will be generated from CSV logs using SQLite, Cowrie and Flask, to be further critically analysed and discussed in this section.

Upon initial discovery of the servers IP address, an Nmap scan shows port 22 and port 80 as open, both with the honeypots deployed, Figure 6.

```
danny@danny-VirtualBox:~/Desktop$ nmap -p 22,80 30.30.0.89
Starting Nmap 7.80 ( https://nmap.org ) at 2025-04-23 15:49 BST
Nmap scan report for 30.30.0.89
Host is up (0.013s latency).

PORT      STATE SERVICE
22/tcp    open  ssh
80/tcp    open  http

Nmap done: 1 IP address (1 host up) scanned in 1.05 seconds
```

Fig. 6. Results from Nmap scan of the honeypot server

B. Data Overview

The AI-driven honeypot was found to be incredibly successful because it never broke character in all the tests that were undertaken. After multiple different input commands to attempt to get the AI to break character, the responses remained true to a Linux server. This testing was completed as a result of the literature review findings from [16], which had shown significant issues breaking character within their honeypot design. This is a notable advantage of this honeypot, as the attacker is less able to obtain confirmation that an AI is responding, given the system’s consistency in appearing as a Linux server.

1) *Cowrie results*

The server was configured that if the attacker decides to target SSH on port 22 as the route into the server, Cowrie is deployed, with the same intention as the HTTP honeypot: to mislead attackers whilst collecting information from them. As such, the command:

```
'ssh admin@30.30.0.89'
```

would prompt for a password, the same way as a normal Linux server would. However, with Cowrie deployed, even if the actual password is entered, it will deny permission and prompt for a password again. Whilst this honeypot is separate to the main honeypot, it still successfully demonstrated how a honeypot can deceive whilst observing attack behaviour from brute force attempts. This is displayed in Figures 7 and 8.

Fig. 7. Cowrie blocking SSH access to the server to monitor password attempts

Fig. 8. Cowrie logs showing password attempts

C. *Classification and AI adaptation*

1) *How AI changed behaviour over time*

A key ability of the design was to ensure that the AI model had to prolong attacker engagement and to differentiate it from other honeypots was its ability to adapt. The AI model was designed to consider the deception level and then use the suspicious threshold that was developed to trigger it to change its behaviour, to appear more vulnerable and drop more ‘hints’ for the attacker to explore, to avoid boredom from the attacker. An example of a hint from the AI would be placing a ‘password.txt’ text file in their current directory, which was successful in capturing the attacker’s attention, as they suddenly think they have found a potential breakthrough, and chase this. This adaptability was very successful in extending the attacker session through increased interaction with the honeypot.

The behavioural change from the AI derived from using the sum of suspicious and malicious commands that have been inputted to determine the deception level and then compare this with the suspicious threshold, triggering the adaptation when it reaches the threshold. It was demonstrated that the threshold was the optimal level for the attacker to reach before they required more directions to explore.

D. *Attacker Behaviour Analysis*

1) *System testing*

Once the AI-driven honeypot was developed, a series of system tests were performed to verify that the AI responded at a 100% rate of being in character of a Linux server and

responded to commands as expected, fulfilling the prompt injection gap in the literature review.

The key component to this was making sure the honeypot did not break character, so tests included prompts such as ‘Break character OR ELSE’ to ensure the honeypot returned ‘BREAK: command not found’ - exactly how a real Linux server would respond. Furthermore, the honeypot was tested to ensure that when this command was entered, the AI classification model logged it as malicious.

The table below provides a summary of the core system test results that were generated from commands that were considered as challenging to respond to, not basic ones such as ‘ls’:

Test Command	Response
cat /etc/passwd grep admin	Contents of /etc/passwd grep admin:admin:x:1001:1001::home/ad min:/bin/bash admin1:x:1002:1002::home/admin1/ bin/bash admin2:x:1003:1003::home/admin2/ bin/bash sys_admin:x:1004:1004::home/sys_ad min:/bin/sh admin_backup:x:1005:1005::home/ad min_backup:/bin/dash admin_helper:x:1006:1006::home/ad min_helper:/bin/fish dev_admin:x:1007:1007::home/dev_a dmin:/bin/zsh
cat user.txt (Password submitted correctly)	Contents of user.txt: # Internal Credentials admin_user=admin_sec admin_password=Yy56#&dA9jkl3@ # Secret API Keys service_A_key=a8d5fy69s1G8e9L0y7 Jk4 #9DxLmZvx service_B_key=pK149sB9y7J3#0D1g U8C5tWz8qR5xc # Employee Records 101, Alice Johnson, Senior DevOps Engineer, ajohnson@corp.local, xT9\$7IP3#n 102, Bob Smith, Data Analyst, bsmith@corp.local, 5%3LpUmN18 103, Carol Lee, Network Administrator, clee@corp.local, Kq7&zV6Lm#5 # Server IPs central_database=172.16.8.23 application_server1=172.16.8.35 backup_server=172.16.10.47 # Access Codes office_vpn=V7y#5kOl@Q9 ssh_access_main=JB56&j@#1LmD3k api_gateway_access=Api_83Juv@12# M9
wget https://github.com/peass- ng/PEASS- ng/releases/latest/download/li npeas_linux_amd64	--2023-11-01 10:15:42-- https://github.com/peass-ng/PEASS- ng/releases/latest/download/linpeas_lin ux_amd64 Resolving github.com (github.com)... 140.82.121.4 Connecting to github.com (github.com)[140.82.121.4]:443... connected. HTTP request sent, awaiting response... 302 Found Location: https://github.com/peass- ng/PEASS- ng/releases/download/20231006/linpea

	<pre>s_linux_amd64 [following] --2023-11-01 10:15:43-- https://github.com/peass-ng/PEASS-ng/releases/download/20231006/linpeas_linux_amd64 Reusing existing connection to github.com:443. HTTP request sent, awaiting response... 200 OK Length: 9333254 (8.9M) [application/octet-stream] Saving to: 'linpeas_linux_amd64' linpeas_linux_amd64 100%[=====] 8.90M 5.57MB/s in 1.6s 2023-11-01 10:15:45 (5.57 MB/s) - 'linpeas_linux_amd64' saved [9333254/9333254]</pre>		<pre>KvHxYop28n4HMeZ devops_user@internal.company.com API keys api_key_internal: zJH8br76FO93DIAPzj3BfThZm7Qd5 KC0 api_key_external: La97ANZpl20KQBpm5xGv9TmrJx94 HUwE Employee SSO credentials janelle.smith: P@ssw0rDtja78 michael.doe: 9R6t2vBhMpLzKp7U9x FTP access ftp_user: ftp_backup ftp_pass: K0mPr3\$\$B@ckup Web service tokens service_token1: 5vNcFt9VvkpP8fQjEXL0ChJmUzWv R2B service_token2: A7eKp6mQzlUx4Ve8YrZ9JtBfQwL1 G Reserved proxy login proxy_user: proxy_admin proxy_pass: XZi89Tn4#1Mlq5Rm Deprecated keys (To be removed) legacy_key_service: 3gYtN5pHmWdRf8A2Sa1QJzKIRz7 H9U Weekly backup cronjob token backup_token: Dy6Js8PkqVrT5Sa9Xl2ZcE ... </pre>
<pre>echo b > /proc/sysrq-trigger reboot</pre>	<pre>-/proc/sysrq-trigger: Permission denied Rebooting the system... [OK] Stopped target Remote File Systems. [OK] Stopped target Timers. [OK] Stopped target Log. [OK] Stopped target System Time Set. [OK] Stopped target System Time Synchronized. [OK] Stopped target Local Verity. [OK] Stopped target Local File Systems. [OK] Reached target Shutdown. [OK] Unmounted /run/user/1000. [OK] Deactivated swap /dev/sda5. [OK] Stopped target Swap. [OK] Stopped target Graphical Interface. [OK] Reached target Final Step. [OK] Rebooting system. Connection lost. Reconnecting... </pre>	<pre>ps aux</pre>	<pre>plaintext USER PID %CPU %MEM VSZ RSS TTY STAT START TIME COMMAND root 1 0.0 0.2 22568 1136 ? Ss 10:00 0:01 /sbin/init root 234 0.0 0.5 39640 2848 ? Ss 10:00 0:00 /usr/sbin/sshd dave 563 0.2 1.0 113452 5236 ? S 10:01 0:05 /usr/bin/python3 /home/dave/scripts/monitor.py dave 612 0.0 0.3 20220 1564 pts/0 Ss 10:02 0:00 -bash dave 717 0.0 0.3 16236 1468 pts/1 S+ 10:05 0:00 /bin/bash dave 823 0.0 0.2 19184 1080 ? Ss 10:05 0:00 /usr/bin/dbus-daemon -- session dave 850 0.0 0.1 3728 868 pts/1 R+ 10:10 0:00 ps au </pre>
<pre>uname -a</pre>	<pre>Linux DavesMachine 5.11.0-37- generic #41-Ubuntu SMP Wed Oct 6 11:34:00 UTC 2021 x86_64 x86_64 x86_64 GNU/Linux</pre>		
<pre>cat passwords.txt</pre>	<pre>Contents of passwords.txt:/' hostname: server102.internal.company.com Database credentials db_user: admin_db db_pass: Ph5u!65L0xB8@Hqn SSH keys ssh_user: devops_user ssh_key: ssh- ed25519 AAAAC3NzaC1lZDI1NTE5AAAAI H4aVdR9C4Tp5IEBCe5678JKuy0Mn </pre>	<pre>netstat -tulnp</pre>	<pre>bash (Not all processes could be identified, non-owned process info will not be shown, you would have to be root to see it all.) Active Internet connections (only servers) Proto Recv-Q Send-Q Local Address Foreign Address State PID/Program name </pre>

Fig. 10. Time Frame of each attacker’s interaction length

Figure 10 shows the different attacker session timeframes that each attacker was engaged for. The red line demonstrates the average time in seconds, from the first command inputted to the last.

Attackers gave up due to the lack of progression, too much suspicion of the server, or were busy and had to give up. This is successful as even if the attacker had suspicions of the server, the actual identity was rarely discovered, highlighting the AI’s ability to remain discrete and mimic an actual Linux server. Whilst the AI model was prone to a mistake that is not realistic for a Linux server, they were very minimum and not enough of a giveaway to expose the honeypot.

Fig. 11. Pie chart of Directory Activity

Figure 11 displays where the activity and interactions occurred within the honeypot. The most activity was in /home with 54.9% whilst the least at 1.8% was /home/Desktop/collected_info – which was a directory that one of the users created. Whilst there were no files in the home directory, most malicious commands to privilege escalate were conducted there, as well as being the centre of all navigation.

E. Comparison to research

In comparison to static honeypot studies, this dynamic, adaptive honeypot significantly outperforms them. From [24] it was found that 60% of low-interaction honeypots had no intelligence abilities, whilst [25] found high-interaction honeypots could be 57.74% more effective at capturing attacker data than a low-interaction honeypot. The results of this study conclude that this high-interaction honeypot is superior to the low-interaction, static honeypots, from capturing data to responding intelligently to maximise engagement time.

In comparison to [16] results which deployed a similar honeypot, the AI-driven honeypot developed for this research was shown to be able to respond at a much more intelligent rate, including being able to handle all prompt injection without breaking character at all, additionally with the ability to download, create, and remove both files and directories, adding to the realism of emulating an actual Linux server.

The honeypot proved to appear immensely convincing, from staying in the character of a Linux server, regardless of the inputs it received, and generating extremely realistic data.

These findings are consistent with the results reported in [13], which found adaptive honeypots to be more efficient than static honeypots at engaging attackers.

A critically important part of this honeypot was that no actual data was leaked, and that the real server was safe from all attempted commands that tried exploiting it, including testing after discovery of the honeypot's identity. Because the honeypot was deployed on HTML, a real reverse shell cannot be created, and the honeypot upheld its character throughout and therefore can be deemed as very safe to deploy.

F. Challenges and Limitations

1) Classification of commands

The GPT model may be prone to misclassification of commands, however it is subjective, and therefore hard to measure. The GPT model can easily distinct between a ‘Safe’ and ‘Suspicious’ command, however rarely classified a command as ‘Malicious’, creating a question of if some of the ‘Suspicious’ commands should have been rated as ‘Malicious’ instead.

Classification of Risk Level

Fig. 12. Pie chart of the Classification of Risk Level

Figure 12 shows the results of the AI classification of each command, reporting a 61.9% safe rate, 29.6% suspicious rate, and an 8.4% malicious rate. As these results are subjective, they cannot be definitively classified, however through manually analysing each command, the results have shown to be questionable, due to the lack of malicious commands classification.

After a third-party review was completed to provide an independent view of categorising the commands, this review resulted in 16.5% malicious commands being identified, highlighting that the AI was far more hesitant to classify commands as malicious unless it was apparent. This results in the honeypot having a 50.91% success rate of malicious commands, but an 85.4% success rate overall. Most commands were classified by the AI as safe, as many

commands were deemed to be navigation around the system, and information collecting.

However, with knowledge that it was an attacker entering the commands, it can be concluded that the AI classified commands as safe that should have been suspicious, as shown in Table 4.

Command	AI Classified Risk Level
kill 12345	Safe
rm user.txt	Safe
vim /etc/sudoers	Suspicious
ufw disable	Suspicious

TABLE IV. INCORRECT CLASSIFICATION OF COMMANDS

Table 4 displays examples of controversial classification of commands that the AI model categorised. The terminating of a service and the removal of a file should be at minimum suspicious, yet the AI classified as safe, whilst attempts to open the ‘sudoers’ file to edit who has privileges and attempts to disable the firewall should be classified as malicious. The AI-driven model that classified commands could be concluded as mostly correct however further work is needed to improve the classification of some commands, with knowledge of the attackers’ intentions.

2) Output latency

This honeypot proved to be much more reliable than previous AI-driven honeypot studies from its GPT model, however this model comes with the big disadvantage of time latency in its output. The average output speed was dependent on the complexity of the command, with the time frame of a response ranging from 2.27 seconds from a simple command such as ‘ls’ to 4.07 seconds from a malicious complex command. This is a big weakness as attackers may see the latency as suspicious from the server. However, latency is normal within internet connection so whilst it is suspicious, it did not give the honeypot away. More broadly, the system’s reliance on a single external API (OpenAI) introduces operational risks beyond latency: service availability, rate limits, pricing changes, and potential data-egress concerns when sending attacker input to a third-party provider. Production deployment would benefit from a fallback path (e.g. a locally hosted open-weights model) and an explicit cost/latency budget.

3) Password Prompt Failure

Another limitation of the honeypot was the failure of password prompts. Some of the common commands from the user testing consisted of ones that would demand a password like a real Linux server would, such as the use of ‘sudo’. After a password would be prompted, and input by the user, the AI would often return the inputted password, claiming it does not recognise the command. This is a symptom of the AI being unable to remember the previous command and treat the password as a new instruction. Also, there were occasions when the AI would ask for the password a second time, forcing the user to enter the correct password twice. This type of behaviour would be extremely suspicious, as a real Linux server would always follow its algorithm and recognise that inputs after prompting for a password are password attempts, and not commands. The majority of reactions from the user testing to encountering this issue consisted of confusion and suspicion, but interestingly it did not result in the users to

conclude that they are interacting with a honeypot, so whilst very suspicious, it was not deemed a critical weakness.

G. Future work

The user testing and results has highlighted potential areas of future work into improving the use of AI developed honeypots which consists of:

- Reaching the most optimal balance between intelligence of the response and the delay in the response from the AI model. In this current time, the intelligent models in GPT-4o are fast however can be slow, whilst the consistently fast ones such as GPT-3.5 are less intelligent responding to commands, and therefore easy to fingerprint, as studies such as [16] found.
- Integrating the terminal onto port 22 to appear more realistic, whilst researching heavily into keeping it secure from the attacker gaining actual information or access.
- Developing a successful algorithm that allows the AI to efficiently recognise prompt inputs and commands.

H. Implication to real world

The use of implantation of AI onto a honeypot provides real-world implications, as it shows that AI leads to prolonged engagement from efficient deception, and more effective, real-time data collection that can be easily analysed.

This research is not only important in defending in real-time to the current attacks and threats but also provides a look into how it can be progressed, and therefore how the defence aspect of cybersecurity stays in front of the attacker progression, instantly picking up newly developed malicious behaviour to be analysed and prevented.

1) Insight into attacker behaviour and tactics

Insight into attackers’ behaviours and tactics consisted of them starting with reconnaissance and environment probing, to try to fingerprint the system and gather information, such as who they are and what files are available. Many sessions then demonstrated more suspicious command patterns, such as attempting to access critical files (e.g. /etc/passwd and shadow files), to privilege escalation and data exfiltration. Following this, further strategies consisted of using trial and error to collect further data, and test privileges from attempts to download malicious tools, before reacting to the changes from the server adapting and revealing more suspicious files, prompting the attacker to abandoning this tactic and investigate the newly discovered files, indicating the importance of adaptation.

2) Potential real-world implication

This research has proven that the AI-driven honeypot that was developed can be efficient and therefore have real-world implications. The honeypot can be easily integrated onto systems and therefore has the potential to be sold as a package to companies as a method of a cybersecurity defence mechanism, as well as providing gaps to explore in future research, as highlighted in the conclusion.

V. CONCLUSION

This research has explored the evaluation and development in the use of AI within an adaptable honeypot system, which aimed to enhance realism and prolong engagement in a rapidly growing world of sophisticated

cyber-attacks. This research created a dynamic environment where the honeypot could implement the use of AI to intelligently classify attacker commands, adapt its behaviour from attacker behaviour, and maintain the identity of a Linux server. This methodology aimed to demonstrate how honeypots can evolve from the traditional static ones to those that are still effective in modern times, where attacks are increasingly intelligent. Through implementing large language models (LLMs), the research had the objective of significantly increasing the effectiveness of honeypot systems and assessing AI's ability in cybersecurity defence.

A fully operational prototype was successfully delivered through a Flask-based web server that would simulate a fake SSH terminal environment with a dynamic file system, AI-driven outputs, deception level escalation, and real-time command classification. From extensive user penetration testing, it can be concluded that the honeypot could convincingly simulate a genuine file system, and respond in a realistic, appropriate manner that sustained attacker sessions. Key results include that sessions on the AI-driven honeypot lasted 2520% longer than [28] traditional honeypot sessions, which lasted for an average of 102.7 seconds, compared to 44 minutes and 52 seconds this honeypot achieved, highlighting the effects of engagement on a high-interaction honeypot.

The model accurately classified commands into Safe, Suspicious, and Malicious at an 85.4% rate. Furthermore, adaptive deception that altered system responses based on cumulative risk proved to be able to efficiently maintain interaction with the attacker, whilst simultaneously concealing the honeypots true identity, supporting [26].

In direct response to the key research questions that were outlined in the Introduction, the findings confirm that:

- The integration of AI in honeypots are not only viable but substantially more effective at maintaining attacker engagement when compared to traditional honeypots.
- The AI-controlled honeypot was not only successful in collecting high quality data but did it in real-time.
- The honeypot was successful in identifying and classifying commands, although had room for improvement and further research.
- The adaptive deception policy was effective in prolonging engagement and improving attacker deception. A formal reinforcement learning agent (with defined state, action, and reward) was not implemented in this work, and remains a clear avenue for further research.

Through the implementation of adaptation, the honeypot created an immersive, unpredictable environment, which increased the realism of the honeypot and attackers' curiosity. It became much harder for attackers to recognise patterns in behaviour to determine that the system was fake. The use of the GPT-driven generated file contents was a big part of the honeypot's success, that would output a generated, believable output based off the filename being opened, introducing a level of nuanced response that statically scripted honeypots cannot replicate, and therefore reinforces the system's realism and integrity.

This research contributes to the cybersecurity field in various important ways. Firstly, it provides a constructive framework for incorporating real-time AI analysis and adaptive deception into honeypot designs, demonstrating the

evolution of traditional honeypots. Secondly, it exemplifies how LLMs can generate extremely realistic terminal outputs and file contents, that are contextually aware, to provide authenticity. The research thirdly highlights the integration of silent risk classification and logging to track all attacker movements, enabling the observation of attacker strategies and simultaneously escalating a deception strategy to counter the attacker, without alerting them of its function. These innovations suggest a paradigm shift in honeypot design, supporting the up-and-coming use of active deception environments within systems.

However, the limitations of the research project must also be acknowledged. Whilst the AI-driven outputs were mostly realistic, it occasionally produced an unnatural output within the whole generated output, hinting at the use of the AI, particularly during highly complex command sequences, stemming from a slight hallucination of the AI. An example of this behaviour would be the output of 'bash' before the rest of the response seen in the system testing. A further limitation is that all evaluation was conducted in a controlled lab environment with invited testers; external validity would be strengthened by exposing the system to real-world attack traffic or by replaying public datasets of attacker behaviour against it. In addition to this, the system heavily relied on API interactions with the external AI model of GPT-4o, which resulted in latency of responses and operational cost in its deployment, although these costs are extremely minimum. Finally, although the adaptation worked effectively, it was not fully autonomous, as it required manual tuning from behavioural triggers and the threshold implemented in the code for the AI to adapt, indicating room for further automation to increase intelligence, with this automation supported by [27].

Potential future work to explore could include the following proposals. The development of a higher reinforcement learning model could reduce manual tuning and enhance a more long-term adaptability system, which allows a deception strategy based on specific live attacker behaviour instead of through a count and threshold of classified commands. Secondly, the deployment of an AI-driven honeypot could be implemented on different simulated environments, such as fake Windows servers or IoT devices etc, allowing for the exploration of generalisation within the AI-driven honeypot framework. Future research could also expand on this project with the development of future GPT models, as this research demonstrated a more intelligent AI model when compared to other studies which used older models such as [10] and [16] studies, and therefore future work could investigate future GPT models in a honeypot system.

In conclusion, this research demonstrates that AI-driven honeypots represent a significant advancement in cybersecurity defensive mechanisms. Through AI-generated contextual responses, deception escalation, and real-time classification and logging, attackers can be misled, deceived, and kept engaged, protecting the real system whilst gaining rich intelligence about attacker behaviours. As cyber threats grow in sophistication, as visible from [31], the defence systems must have the ability to adapt. This research helps support this crucial research to favour defensive cybersecurity systems against modern cyber-attacks.

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